

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at AICRIP, India, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
TN1	18	6.4 a	95	4	1.8	37	1.60	1.68
IR26	7	5.6 ab	80	3	1.4	26	1.10	1.38
Habiganj DW8	8	5.2 ab	80	3	1.4	35	1.15	1.44
Pankhari 203	14	4.8 bc	75	2	1.1	22	0.80	1.07
Latisail	8	4.8 bc	75	3	2.2	30	1.25	1.67
Kataribhog	8	4.8 bc	75	2	1.3	24	1.00	1.33
Ambemohar 159	8	4.2 cd	85	3	1.6	38	1.40	1.65
Ptb 18	8	3.7 cd	85	2	1.5	40	1.25	1.47
IR34	8	3.7 cd	70	1	1.0	22	0.70	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	8	2.8 d	75	1	1.0	27	0.75	1.00
Max or av	18	4.6	80	4	1.4	30	1.10	1.37

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

DW8, IR26, and TN1 (see table).

About 30% of 729 seedlings inoculated by the viruliferous insects became infected. There seemed to be no remarkable differences among the 10 rice varieties as far as tungro transmission was concerned. However, the insects were

less efficient in transmitting the tungro virus to IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Pankhari 203 than to the other varieties (see table). Those three might be more resistant to tungro than the others in the test. ■

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines

K. C. Ling and M. S. A. Miah, International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines

As part of the RTV Collaborative Project, an IRRI study investigated the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* in the IRRI greenhouse from 15 May to 28 June, 1978. In two

trials, 800 adult insects — 40 females and 40 males on 10 varieties — were given an acquisition access time of 4 days on tungro-diseased seedlings. The insects survived 1 to 23 days. The average life span was 4.8 days (5.0 days for female insects, and 4.6 days for the male).

The short life span on IR34, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Ptb 18, and Pankhari 203 indicated that these varieties were more resistant to the insect than were the six others in the test (see table).

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at IRRI, Philippines, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Habiganj DW8	23	7.3 a	14	1	1.0	3	0.14	1.00
Kataribhog	14	7.2 a	18	2	1.2	4	0.19	1.07
IR26	12	5.9 b	81	4	1.6	31	1.24	1.52
TN1	15	5.7 b	89	4	1.5	36	1.28	1.44
Ambemohar 159	19	5.5 b	48	3	1.2	16	0.56	1.18
Latisail	13	5.4 b	71	5	1.5	27	0.99	1.39
Pankhari 203	11	3.8 c	5	2	1.3	2	0.05	1.00
Ptb 18	9	2.6 d	45	2	1.0	18	0.45	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	6	2.6 d	48	2	1.0	20	0.49	1.03
IR34	6	2.3 d	54	2	1.0	25	0.55	1.02
Max or av	23	4.8	47	5	1.5	18	0.60	1.17

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Of 2,637 seedlings of 10 rice varieties inoculated by the insects, 18% developed tungro. Insect efficiency in transmitting the tungro virus was lowest with Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, and Kataribhog. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Anatomical studies of rice varieties tolerant of and susceptible to complete submergence at seedling stage

S. Karin and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Leaf sheath and leaf blades from 12 varieties were collected in 10-day-old seedlings to study the anatomical differences between varieties tolerant of the susceptible to complete submergence.

The number of vascular bundles on the first and second leaf blades varied among the varieties; however, the difference between the tolerant and susceptible varieties was not significant.

The leaf sheath is characterized by the presence of a large air space which alternates with the vascular bundles and is separated by narrow bands of parenchyma. The number of vascular bundles in the first and second leaf sheaths of the tolerant and susceptible varieties did not show any difference or correlation to submergence tolerance.

The role of the air space in submergence has not been studied. It possibly is important because it may serve as an oxygen reservoir or, if the leaf tips are above the water level, as passageway for transporting oxygen from the leaf blade to the roots. Thus, the air space might play an important role in maintaining the integrity of the cells. On the other hand, the occurrence of large air spaces may result in spongy, weak leaf sheaths that would make the plant prone to lodging when the water level recedes.

The percentage of air space per unit area was negatively and significantly correlated to submergence tolerance ($r = -0.5997^*$). The air spaces on the first leaf